

Pechmann Condensation—I Use of Catalytic Amount of Condensing Agents

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It has been found that the Pechmann condensation could be effected using only a catalytic amount of the reagent. Excellent yields are obtained with concentrated sulphuric acid, phosphorus trichloride and phosphorus oxychloride. Basic reagents do effect the condensation, though in poor yields.

Pechmann condensation between phenols and β -ketonic esters is an important method for the synthesis of coumarins¹. A number of condensing agents have been used. In almost all the procedures reported a considerable amount of the condensing agent has been employed². Israelstam and Barris³ have successfully carried out the condensation using a small amount of sulphuric acid as a condensing agent.

In the present case, the condensation has been carried out using a small amount of various condensing agents. The amount used was one-fortieth of the calculated equimolecular proportion. The reagents used were concentrated sulphuric acid, phosphorus trichloride, phosphorus oxychloride, phosphorus pentoxide, anhydrous aluminium chloride, anhydrous zinc chloride, bromine, iodine, pyridine, piperidine, dry ammonia and an anion exchange resin (amberlite IRA-400). The reactants used were resorcinol and ethyl acetoacetate.

The conditions used were at room temperature (28–32°) for 24, 48 or 144 (in some cases) hours without a solvent, at room temperature for 24 hrs with chloroform as a solvent, and on a steam bath (100°) for one and a half hour. The results are given in Tables I to III.

TABLE I

Using different catalysts

Catalyst	mg.	Yield	
Room Temp. : 28–32°		g.	%
		24 Hours	
I ₂	320	7.1	81
Br ₂	200	6.0	69
c. H ₂ SO ₄	140	8.1	92
PCl ₃	170	8.0	93
POCl ₃	190	8.0	91
P ₂ O ₅	170	0.3	3
AlCl ₃	160	1.8	20

1. S. M. Sethna and N. M. Shah, *Chem. Rev.*, 1945, **36**, 1.
2. S. Sethna and R. Phadke, *Organic Reactions*, Roger Adams. Vol. VII, p. 1, Wiley, New York, 1953.
3. S. S. Israelstam and E. Barris, *Chem. Ind.*, 1958, 1430.

TABLE II

Under different conditions

Catalyst	Yield		
	I	II	III
I ₂	7.1	4.0	2.0
Br ₂	6.0	3.0	2.0
c H ₂ SO ₄	8.3	8.2	7.0
PCl ₃	8.3	8.2	8.2
POCl ₃	8.4	8.0	8.4
P ₂ O ₅	2.0	1.4	0.2
AlCl ₃	4.6	2.0	7.5

I : 48 hrs at room temperature (28–32°)

II : 24 hrs at room temperature (28–32°) in chloroform (8.0 g)

III : One and a half hour on a steam-bath.

TABLE III

Using basic reagents

Catalyst	Yield	
	I	II
Dry NH ₃ passed for 2 minutes	1.3	...
Piperidine (0.5 g.)	0.4	0.2
Pyridine (6.5 g.)	Nil	0.6
Amberlite IRA-400 (2.0 g.)	2.0	↓.7

I : 144 hrs at room temperature (28–32°)

II : 90 mins at 150°.

Phosphorus oxychloride and trichloride gave excellent yields when used at room temperature (28–32°) for 24 hrs with or without a solvent (chloroform) or on a steam-bath (100°) for one and a half hour. Concentrated sulphuric acid gave an excellent yield at room temperature (28–32°) with or without a solvent which decreased on a steam bath for one and a half hour. This may be due to sulphonation and other side reactions. Phosphorus pentoxide gave very poor to poor yields. Anhydrous zinc chloride failed to bring about the condensation under these conditions. Anhydrous aluminium chloride gave poor yields at room temperature for 24 hrs. with or without a solvent. The yield was fairly good when the reaction period was increased to 48 hrs and very good on a steam-bath for one and half hour. Bromine and iodine gave good to very good yields at room temperature for 24 hrs without a solvent.

These experiments clearly point out that hitherto a large excess of the reagents was being used even though the consideration could be effected using only a catalytic amount of the same. This was verified by carrying out a reaction taking larger quantities of the reactants, when also an excellent yield was obtained. Phosphorus oxychloride on a steam-bath for one and half hour appears to be the best amongst these.

It was also observed that reagents like dry ammonia, piperidine, pyridine and an anionic resin (amberlite IRA 400) effected the condensation at room temperature for 144 hrs, however the yields were very poor. It is thus evident that basic reagents do bring about the condensation, though they are not as effective.

EXPERIMENTAL

A mixture of resorcinol (5.5 g.; 0.05 mole) and ethyl acetoacetate (6.5 g.; 0.05 mole) with different condensing agents (0.00125 mole) was kept at the requisite temperature (28–32°) for the requisite period. The mixture was poured into crushed ice and the product was collected, washed, dried and weighed. 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin formed was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 184–185°. Pechmann and Duisberg⁴ give m.p. 185°.

Pechmann condensation of resorcinol and ethyl acetoacetate using catalytic amount of phosphorus oxychloride: Resorcinol (55.0 g.; 0.5 mole), ethyl acetoacetate (65.0 g.; 0.5 mole) and phosphorus oxychloride (1.92 g.; 0.0125 mole) were mixed and heated on a steam-bath for 90 mins. The reaction product was poured into ice-cold water. 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was collected, washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 186°. Yield: 82 g.

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4. H. von Pechmann and C. Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2119.

